

DATASET DESCRIPTION

A List of features

Table 1. Numbered list of features in our dataset.

Num	Feature	Values or units	Type
#001	Sex	Male, Female	Binary
#002	Age	[years]	Continuous
#003	Height	[m]	Continuous
#004	Weight	[kg]	Continuous
#005	Body mass index (BMI)	[kg/m ²]	Continuous
#006	Obesity	No, Yes	Binary
#007	Alcohol use	No = 0, Ex = 1, Yes = 2	Ordinal
#008	Tobacco use	No = 0, Ex = 1, Yes = 2	Ordinal
#009	Lives at nursing home	No, Yes	Binary
#010	Comorbidity: Hypertension	No, Yes	Binary
#011	Comorbidity: Diabetes mellitus	No, Yes	Binary
#012	Comorbidity: Dyslipidemia	No, Yes	Binary
#013	Comorbidity: Cardiovascular	No, Yes	Binary
#014	Comorbidity: Chronic heart failure	No, Yes	Binary
#015	Comorbidity: Cerebrovascular	No, Yes	Binary
#016	Comorbidity: Broncho	No, Asthma, ILD, COPD, Others	Categorical
#017	Comorbidity: Renal	No, Yes	Binary
#018	Comorbidity: Hepatic	No, Yes	Binary
#019	Comorbidity: Ischemia	No, Yes	Binary
#020	Comorbidity: Peptic ulcer	No, Yes	Binary
#021	Comorbidity: Thyroid	No, Yes	Binary
#022	Comorbidity: Autoimmune	No, Yes	Binary
#023	Comorbidity: Transplants	No, Yes	Binary
#024	Comorbidity: Cancer-neoplasia	No, Yes	Binary
#025	Comorbidity: Immune-HIV	No, Yes	Binary
#026	Comorbidity: Overall	No, Yes	Binary
#027	Comorbidity: Charlson index	—	Integer
#028	Pneumonia: CURB-65 score	—	Integer
#029	Pneumonia: PSI score	—	Integer
#030	Sepsis: qSOFA score	—	Integer
#031	Symptoms: Cough	No, Yes	Binary
#032	Symptoms: Expectoration	No, Yes	Binary
#033	Symptoms: Dyspnea	No, Yes	Binary
#034	Symptoms: Myalgia	No, Yes	Binary
#035	Symptoms: Confusion	No, Yes	Binary
#036	Symptoms: Thorax pain	No, Yes	Binary
#037	Symptoms: Anosmia	No, Yes	Binary
#038	Symptoms: Fever	No = 0, Febricula = 1, Fever = 2	Ordinal
#039	Symptoms: Digestive-gastro	No, Yes	Binary
#040	Symptoms: Overall	No, Yes	Binary
#041	Symptoms: Days	—	Integer

Num	Feature	Values or units	Type
#042	Emergency treatm: ACEI-AIIRB	No, Yes	Binary
#043	Emergency treatm: Statin	No, Yes	Binary
#044	Emergency treatm: Anticoagulant	No, Yes	Binary
#045	Emergency treatm: Antiplatelet	No, Yes	Binary
#046	Emergency treatm: Corticosteroids	No, Inhaled, Oral, Missing	Categorical
#047	Admission status: Body temperature	[$^{\circ}C$]	Continuous
#048	Admission status: Systolic blood pressure	[$mmHg$]	Continuous
#049	Admission status: Diastolic blood pressure	[$mmHg$]	Continuous
#050	Admission status: Respiratory rate	[min^{-1}]	Continuous
#051	Admission status: Heart rate	[min^{-1}]	Continuous
#052	Admission status: SpO ₂	[%]	Continuous
#053	Admission status: FiO ₂	[fraction]	Continuous
#054	Admission status: SpO ₂ /FiO ₂	[ratio]	Continuous
#055	Admission status: SpO ₂ /RespRate	[%/min ⁻¹]	Continuous
#056	Pulmonary status: Crackles	No, Yes	Binary
#057	Pulmonary status: Infiltr. X-Ray	No, Unilateral, Multilobar unilateral, Bilateral, Missing	Categorical
#058	Pulmonary status: Infiltr. type	No, Alveolar, Consolidation, Interstitial, Missing	Categorical
#059	Pulmonary status: Infiltration, Num. lobes	—	Integer
#060	Pulmonary status: Pleural effusion	No, Yes	Binary
#061	Blood test: Glucose	[mg/dL]	Continuous
#062	Blood test: Urea [log ₁₀]	[mg/dL]	Continuous
#063	Blood test: Creatinine [log ₁₀]	[mg/dL]	Continuous
#064	Blood test: Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) [log ₁₀]	[mg/dL]	Continuous
#065	Blood test: Sodium	[mEq/L]	Continuous
#066	Blood test: Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) [log ₁₀]	[U/L]	Continuous
#067	Blood test: Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) [log ₁₀]	[U/L]	Continuous
#068	Blood test: C-Reactive protein (CRP) [log ₁₀]	[mg/L]	Continuous
#069	Blood test: Procalcitonin (PCT) [log ₁₀]	[$\mu g/L$]	Continuous
#070	Blood test: Hematocrit	[%]	Continuous
#071	Blood test: Leukocytes [log ₁₀]	[$count/\mu L$]	Continuous
#072	Blood test: Lymphocytes [log ₁₀]	[$count/\mu L$]	Continuous
#073	Blood test: Neutrophils [log ₁₀]	[$count/\mu L$]	Continuous
#074	Blood test: Monocytes [log ₁₀]	[$count/\mu L$]	Continuous
#075	Blood test: Basophils [log ₁₀]	[$count/\mu L$]	Continuous
#076	Blood test: Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio (NLR) [log ₁₀]	[ratio]	Continuous
#077	Blood test: Fibrinogen [log ₁₀]	[mg/dL]	Continuous
#078	Blood test: D-dimer [log ₁₀]	[ng/mL]	Continuous
#079	Blood test: Serum IP-10 [log ₁₀]	[pg/mL]	Continuous
#080	Arterial blood gas tests: SatO ₂	[%]	Continuous
#081	Arterial blood gas tests: FiO ₂	[fraction]	Continuous
#082	Arterial blood gas tests: SatO ₂ /FiO ₂	[ratio]	Continuous
#083	COVID-19 diagn: Method	Rapid serology, PCR sputum, PCR nasophar, Missing	Categorical
#084	COVID-19 diagn: Days diagnosed before admission	—	Integer
#085	COVID-19 diagn: Antigens in urine	No, Yes	Binary
#086	Emerg COVID-19 treatm: Antibiotics	No, Beta-lactam, Macrolides, Macrol & Beta, Quinolones, Others	Categorical
#087	Emerg COVID-19 treatm: Chloroquine	No, Yes	Binary
#088	Emerg COVID-19 treatm: Kaletra	No, Yes	Binary
#089	Emerg COVID-19 treatm: Remdesivir	No, Yes	Binary

Num	Feature	Values or units	Type
#090	Emerg COVID-19 treatm: Interferon Beta-1a	No, Yes	Binary
#091	Emerg COVID-19 treatm: IV corticoids	No = 0, Low = 1, High = 2	Ordinal
#092	Emerg COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	No = 0, Prophylaxis = 1, Below therapeutical = 2, Therapeut. = 3, High risk = 4	Ordinal
#093	Demographics per postcode: Population density [$\log_{10}$]	[<i>inhab/km²</i>]	Continuous
#094	Demographics per postcode: Population under 18 years	[%]	Continuous
#095	Demographics per postcode: Population over 65 years	[%]	Continuous
#096	Demographics per postcode: Average age	[<i>years</i>]	Continuous
#097	Demographics per postcode: Average household size	[<i>persons/house</i>]	Continuous
#098	Demographics per postcode: Single-person households	[%]	Continuous
#099	Demographics per postcode: Average personal income	[<i>k€</i>]	Continuous
#100	Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc – PM ₁₀	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#101	Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc – PM _{2.5}	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#102	Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc – O ₃	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#103	Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc – NO ₂	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#104	Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc – NO	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#105	Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc – NO _X	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#106	Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc – SO ₂	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#107	Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc – CO	[mg/m^3]	Continuous
#108	Pollut expos: Chronic, 90 th perc – PM ₁₀	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#109	Pollut expos: Chronic, 90 th perc – PM _{2.5}	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#110	Pollut expos: Chronic, 90 th perc – O ₃	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#111	Pollut expos: Chronic, 90 th perc – NO ₂	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#112	Pollut expos: Chronic, 90 th perc – NO	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#113	Pollut expos: Chronic, 90 th perc – NO _X	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#114	Pollut expos: Chronic, 90 th perc – SO ₂	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#115	Pollut expos: Chronic, 90 th perc – CO	[mg/m^3]	Continuous
#116	Pollut expos: Acute, 50 th perc – PM ₁₀	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#117	Pollut expos: Acute, 50 th perc – PM _{2.5}	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#118	Pollut expos: Acute, 50 th perc – O ₃	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#119	Pollut expos: Acute, 50 th perc – NO ₂	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#120	Pollut expos: Acute, 50 th perc – NO	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#121	Pollut expos: Acute, 50 th perc – NO _X	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#122	Pollut expos: Acute, 50 th perc – SO ₂	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#123	Pollut expos: Acute, 50 th perc – CO	[mg/m^3]	Continuous
#124	Pollut expos: Acute, 90 th perc – PM ₁₀	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#125	Pollut expos: Acute, 90 th perc – PM _{2.5}	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#126	Pollut expos: Acute, 90 th perc – O ₃	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#127	Pollut expos: Acute, 90 th perc – NO ₂	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#128	Pollut expos: Acute, 90 th perc – NO	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#129	Pollut expos: Acute, 90 th perc – NO _X	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#130	Pollut expos: Acute, 90 th perc – SO ₂	[$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Continuous
#131	Pollut expos: Acute, 90 th perc – CO	[mg/m^3]	Continuous

Abbreviations for Table 1 – *ILD*: interstitial lung disease, *COPD*: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, *HIV*: human immunodeficiency virus, *PSI*: pneumonia severity index, *CURB-65*: pneumonia severity score (confusion, urea, respiratory rate, blood pressure, age 65), *qSOFA*: quick sequential organ failure assessment score, *ACEI*: angiotensin-converting-enzyme inhibitors, *AIIRB*: angiotensin II receptor blockers, *IP-10*: interferon gamma inducible protein-10, *PCR*: polymerase chain reaction, *IV*: intravenous, *LMWH*: low molecular weight heparin.

B Cohort characteristics

Abbreviations for Table 2 – *NA*: not available, *IQR*: inter-quartile range, *K-W*: Kruskal-Wallis, *NS*: not significant, *BMI*: body-mass index, *ILD*: interstitial lung disease, *COPD*: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, *HIV*: human immunodeficiency virus, *PSI*: pneumonia severity index, *CURB-65*: pneumonia severity score (confusion, urea, respiratory rate, blood pressure, age 65), *qSOFA*: quick sequential organ failure assessment score, *ACEI*: angiotensin-converting-enzyme inhibitors, *AIIRB*: angiotensin II receptor blockers, *BUN*: blood urea nitrogen, *GGT*: gamma-glutamyl transferase, *LDH*: lactate dehydrogenase, *CRP*: C-reactive protein, *PCT*: procalcitonin, *IP-10*: interferon gamma inducible protein-10, *PCR*: polymerase chain reaction, *IV*: intravenous, *LMWH*: low molecular weight heparin.

Table 2. Cohort characteristics: Overall and by severity group.

Variable	Overall n=1548	By severity			p-value	Effect size
		Low n=712 (46.0%)	Medium n=238 (15.4%)	High n=598 (38.6%)		
<i>Hospital</i>					χ^2	V
A	358 (23.1%)	205 (57.3%)	36 (10.1%)	117 (32.7%)		
B	380 (24.5%)	229 (60.3%)	50 (13.2%)	101 (26.6%)		
C	438 (28.3%)	119 (27.2%)	59 (13.5%)	260 (59.4%)		
D	372 (24.0%)	159 (42.7%)	93 (25.0%)	120 (32.3%)	<0.001	0.225 Medium
<i>Sex</i>					χ^2	V
Male	952 (61.5%)	385 (40.4%)	143 (15.0%)	424 (44.5%)		
Female	596 (38.5%)	327 (54.9%)	95 (15.9%)	174 (29.2%)		
NA	0	0	0	0	<0.001	0.155 Small
<i>Age [years]</i>					K-W	η_H^2
Median	65	60	71	69		
IQR	[53, 77]	[49, 72]	[60, 81]	[57, 79]		
Num. valid	1548 (100%)	712 (100%)	238 (100%)	598 (100%)	<0.001	0.061 Medium
<i>Height [m]</i>					K-W	η_H^2
Median	1.66	1.65	1.65	1.68		
IQR	[1.60, 1.73]	[1.60, 1.72]	[1.58, 1.73]	[1.60, 1.74]		
Num. valid	895 (57.8%)	417 (58.6%)	129 (54.2%)	349 (58.4%)	0.016	0.007 Negligible
<i>Weight [kg]</i>					K-W	η_H^2
Median	78.5	78.0	75.0	80.0		
IQR	[68.0, 89.0]	[66.0, 89.0]	[67.0, 86.0]	[70.0, 90.0]		
Num. valid	982 (63.4%)	466 (65.4%)	141 (59.2%)	375 (62.7%)	0.009	0.008 Negligible
<i>Body mass index (BMI) [kg/m²]</i>					K-W	η_H^2
Median	27.78	27.76	27.14	28.09		
IQR	[25.23, 31.55]	[25.05, 31.74]	[25.07, 30.58]	[25.71, 31.61]		
Num. valid	866 (55.9%)	403 (56.6%)	126 (52.9%)	337 (56.4%)	0.221	NS NS
<i>Obesity</i>					χ^2	V
No	664 (42.9%)	305 (42.8%)	104 (43.7%)	255 (42.6%)		
Yes	343 (22.2%)	162 (22.8%)	44 (18.5%)	137 (22.9%)		
NA	541 (34.9%)	245 (34.4%)	90 (37.8%)	206 (34.4%)	0.483	NS NS
<i>Alcohol use</i>					χ^2	V
No	941 (60.8%)	432 (60.7%)	166 (69.7%)	343 (57.4%)		
Ex	16 (1.0%)	4 (0.6%)	4 (1.7%)	8 (1.3%)		
Yes	54 (3.5%)	26 (3.7%)	5 (2.1%)	23 (3.8%)		
NA	537 (34.7%)	250 (35.1%)	63 (26.5%)	224 (37.5%)	0.242	NS NS
<i>Tobacco use</i>					χ^2	V
No	900 (58.1%)	421 (59.1%)	144 (60.5%)	335 (56.0%)		
Ex	347 (22.4%)	184 (25.8%)	47 (19.7%)	116 (19.4%)		
Yes	83 (5.4%)	42 (5.9%)	14 (5.9%)	27 (4.5%)		
NA	218 (14.1%)	65 (9.1%)	33 (13.9%)	120 (20.1%)	0.346	NS NS
<i>Lives at nursing home</i>					χ^2	V
No	1274 (82.3%)	651 (91.4%)	174 (73.1%)	449 (75.1%)		
Yes	94 (6.1%)	15 (2.1%)	37 (15.5%)	42 (7.0%)		
NA	180 (11.6%)	46 (6.5%)	27 (11.3%)	107 (17.9%)	<0.001	0.209 Small
<i>Comorbidity: Hypertension</i>					χ^2	V
No	801 (51.7%)	432 (60.7%)	96 (40.3%)	273 (45.7%)		
Yes	474 (48.3%)	280 (39.3%)	142 (59.7%)	325 (54.3%)		
NA	0	0	0	0	<0.001	0.165 Small
<i>Comorbidity: Diabetes mellitus</i>					χ^2	V
No	1218 (78.7%)	582 (81.7%)	188 (79.0%)	448 (74.9%)		
Yes	326 (21.1%)	128 (18.0%)	50 (21.0%)	148 (24.7%)		
NA	4 (0.3%)	2 (0.3%)	0	2 (0.3%)	0.011	0.067 Negligible
<i>Comorbidity: Dyslipidemia</i>					χ^2	V
No	973 (62.9%)	475 (66.7%)	128 (53.8%)	370 (61.9%)		
Yes	575 (37.1%)	237 (33.3%)	110 (46.2%)	228 (38.1%)		
NA	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.085 Negligible
<i>Comorbidity: Cardiovascular</i>					χ^2	V
No	1264 (81.7%)	613 (86.1%)	197 (82.8%)	454 (75.9%)		
Yes	284 (18.3%)	99 (13.9%)	41 (17.2%)	144 (24.1%)		
NA	0	0	0	0	<0.001	0.116 Small
<i>Comorbidity: Chronic heart failure</i>					χ^2	V
No	1111 (71.8%)	478 (67.1%)	190 (79.8%)	443 (74.1%)		
Yes	78 (5.0%)	29 (4.1%)	12 (5.0%)	37 (6.2%)		
NA	359 (23.2%)	205 (28.8%)	36 (15.1%)	118 (19.7%)	0.418	NS NS
<i>Comorbidity: Cerebrovascular</i>					χ^2	V
No	1058 (68.3%)	472 (66.3%)	168 (70.6%)	418 (69.9%)		

Variable	Overall		By severity			p-value	Effect size
	n=1548	Low n=712 (46.0%)	Medium n=238 (15.4%)	High n=598 (38.6%)			
Comorbidity: Bronchopathy	Yes	132 (8.5%)	35 (4.9%)	34 (14.3%)	63 (10.5%)	χ^2	0.115 V
	NA	358 (23.1%)	205 (28.8%)	36 (15.1%)	117 (19.6%)		
	No	1232 (79.6%)	559 (78.5%)	203 (85.3%)	470 (78.6%)		
	Asthma	87 (5.6%)	55 (7.7%)	9 (3.8%)	23 (3.8%)		
Comorbidity: ILD	Yes	5 (0.3%)	2 (0.3%)	1 (0.4%)	2 (0.3%)	χ^2	V
	NA	102 (6.6%)	42 (5.9%)	13 (5.5%)	47 (7.9%)		
	Other	122 (7.9%)	54 (7.6%)	12 (5.0%)	56 (9.4%)		
	NA	0	0	0	0		
Comorbidity: Renal	No	1356 (87.6%)	657 (92.3%)	199 (83.6%)	500 (83.6%)	χ^2	V
	Yes	186 (12.0%)	55 (7.7%)	38 (16.0%)	93 (15.6%)		
	NA	6 (0.4%)	0	1 (0.4%)	5 (0.8%)		
	NA	52 (3.4%)	699 (98.2%)	226 (95.0%)	571 (95.5%)		
Comorbidity: Hepatic	No	1496 (96.6%)	13 (1.8%)	12 (5.0%)	27 (4.5%)	χ^2	V
	Yes	52 (3.4%)	0	0	0		
	NA	0	0	0	0		
	NA	1064 (68.7%)	574 (80.6%)	173 (72.7%)	317 (53.0%)		
Comorbidity: Ischemia	No	46 (3.0%)	19 (2.7%)	6 (2.5%)	21 (3.5%)	0.073	NS
	Yes	438 (28.3%)	119 (16.7%)	59 (24.8%)	260 (43.5%)		
	NA	1086 (70.2%)	582 (81.7%)	176 (73.9%)	328 (54.8%)		
	NA	24 (1.6%)	11 (1.5%)	3 (1.3%)	10 (1.7%)		
Comorbidity: Peptic ulcer	Yes	438 (28.3%)	119 (16.7%)	59 (24.8%)	260 (43.5%)	χ^2	V
	NA	1086 (70.2%)	582 (81.7%)	176 (73.9%)	328 (54.8%)		
	NA	24 (1.6%)	11 (1.5%)	3 (1.3%)	10 (1.7%)		
	NA	438 (28.3%)	119 (16.7%)	59 (24.8%)	260 (43.5%)		
Comorbidity: Thyroid	No	664 (42.9%)	382 (53.6%)	77 (32.3%)	205 (34.3%)	χ^2	V
	Yes	73 (4.7%)	52 (7.3%)	9 (3.8%)	12 (2.0%)		
	NA	811 (52.4%)	278 (39.0%)	152 (63.9%)	381 (63.7%)		
	NA	1120 (72.4%)	526 (73.9%)	136 (57.1%)	458 (76.6%)		
Comorbidity: Autoimmune	No	52 (3.4%)	26 (3.7%)	9 (3.8%)	17 (2.8%)	0.369	NS
	Yes	376 (24.3%)	160 (22.5%)	93 (39.1%)	123 (20.6%)		
	NA	1094 (70.7%)	588 (82.6%)	174 (73.1%)	332 (55.5%)		
	NA	16 (1.0%)	5 (0.7%)	6 (1.0%)	6 (1.0%)		
Comorbidity: Transplants	Yes	438 (28.3%)	119 (16.7%)	59 (24.8%)	260 (43.5%)	χ^2	V
	NA	1428 (92.2%)	669 (94.0%)	212 (89.1%)	547 (91.5%)		
	Yes	120 (7.8%)	43 (6.0%)	26 (10.9%)	51 (8.5%)		
	NA	0	0	0	0		
Comorbidity: Cancer, neoplasia	No	1431 (92.4%)	692 (97.2%)	214 (89.9%)	525 (87.8%)	χ^2	V
	Yes	67 (4.3%)	12 (1.7%)	20 (8.4%)	35 (5.9%)		
	NA	50 (3.2%)	8 (1.1%)	4 (1.7%)	38 (6.4%)		
	NA	381 (24.6%)	228 (32.0%)	41 (17.2%)	112 (18.7%)		
Comorbidity: Overall	Yes	1167 (75.4%)	484 (68.0%)	197 (82.8%)	486 (81.3%)	χ^2	V
	NA	0	0	0	0		
	Median	3	2	4	4		
	IQR	[1, 5]	[1, 4]	[2, 6]	[2, 6]		
Comorbidity: Charlson index	Num. valid	1548 (100%)	712 (100%)	238 (100%)	598 (100%)	K-W	η^2_H
	Median	3	2	4	4		
	IQR	[1, 5]	[1, 4]	[2, 6]	[2, 6]		
	Num. valid	1548 (100%)	712 (100%)	238 (100%)	598 (100%)		
Pneumonia: PSI score	Median	70	59	78	83	K-W	η^2_H
	IQR	[53, 92]	[46, 77]	[62, 100]	[65, 109]		
	Num. valid	1287 (83.1%)	640 (89.9%)	200 (84.0%)	447 (74.7%)		
	Num. valid	539 (34.8%)	337 (47.3%)	59 (24.8%)	143 (23.9%)		
Pneumonia: CURB-65 score	0	516 (33.3%)	230 (32.3%)	80 (33.6%)	206 (34.4%)	χ^2	V
	1	361 (23.3%)	125 (17.6%)	68 (28.6%)	168 (28.1%)		
	2	89 (5.7%)	3 (0.4%)	3 (1.3%)	14 (2.3%)		
	3	20 (1.3%)	7 (30.4%)	8 (3.4%)	8 (1.3%)		
Sepsis: qSOFA score	0	791 (51.1%)	502 (70.5%)	131 (55.0%)	158 (26.4%)	χ^2	V
	1	539 (34.8%)	337 (47.3%)	59 (24.8%)	143 (23.9%)		
	2	89 (5.7%)	3 (0.4%)	3 (1.3%)	14 (2.3%)		
	3	20 (1.3%)	7 (30.4%)	8 (3.4%)	8 (1.3%)		

Variable	Overall		Low		By severity		p-value	Effect size
	n=1548		n=712 (46.0%)		Medium n=238 (15.4%)	High n=598 (38.6%)		
	1	274 (17.7%)	84 (11.8%)	41 (17.2%)	149 (24.9%)			
	2	39 (2.5%)	6 (0.8%)	6 (2.5%)	27 (4.5%)			
	3	3 (0.2%)	1 (0.1%)	0	2 (0.3%)			
	NA	441 (28.5%)	119 (16.7%)	60 (13.6%)	262 (43.8%)		<0.001	0.259 Medium
<i>Symptoms: Cough</i>	No	404 (26.1%)	193 (27.1%)	72 (30.3%)	139 (23.2%)		χ^2	V
	Yes	1015 (65.6%)	488 (68.5%)	144 (60.5%)	383 (64.0%)		0.184	NS NS
	NA	129 (8.3%)	31 (4.4%)	22 (9.2%)	76 (12.7%)		χ^2	V
<i>Symptoms: Expectoration</i>	No	1166 (75.3%)	567 (79.6%)	181 (76.1%)	418 (69.9%)			
	Yes	254 (16.4%)	114 (16.0%)	35 (14.7%)	105 (17.6%)		0.255	NS NS
	NA	128 (8.3%)	31 (4.4%)	22 (9.2%)	75 (12.5%)		χ^2	V
<i>Symptoms: Dyspnea</i>	No	754 (48.7%)	387 (54.4%)	133 (55.9%)	234 (39.1%)		<0.001	0.126 Small
	Yes	669 (43.2%)	296 (41.6%)	83 (34.9%)	290 (48.5%)		χ^2	V
	NA	125 (8.1%)	29 (4.1%)	22 (9.2%)	74 (12.4%)		0.091	NS NS
<i>Symptoms: Myalgia</i>	No	1108 (71.6%)	519 (72.9%)	165 (69.3%)	424 (70.9%)		χ^2	V
	Yes	314 (20.3%)	164 (23.0%)	51 (21.4%)	99 (16.6%)		0.091	NS NS
	NA	126 (8.1%)	29 (4.1%)	22 (9.2%)	75 (12.5%)		χ^2	V
<i>Symptoms: Confusion</i>	No	1336 (86.3%)	672 (94.4%)	198 (83.2%)	466 (77.9%)		<0.001	0.177 Small
	Yes	86 (5.6%)	11 (1.5%)	19 (8.0%)	56 (9.4%)		χ^2	V
	NA	126 (8.1%)	29 (4.1%)	21 (8.8%)	76 (12.7%)		0.500	NS NS
<i>Symptoms: Thorax pain</i>	No	1279 (82.6%)	614 (86.2%)	190 (79.8%)	475 (79.4%)		χ^2	V
	Yes	143 (9.2%)	69 (9.7%)	26 (10.9%)	48 (8.0%)		0.500	NS NS
	NA	126 (8.1%)	29 (4.1%)	22 (9.2%)	75 (12.5%)		χ^2	V
<i>Symptoms: Anosmia</i>	No	1320 (85.3%)	572 (80.3%)	212 (89.1%)	536 (89.6%)		<0.001	0.131 Small
	Yes	219 (14.1%)	137 (19.2%)	26 (10.9%)	56 (9.4%)		χ^2	V
	NA	9 (0.6%)	3 (0.4%)	0	6 (1.0%)		0.452	NS NS
<i>Symptoms: Fever</i>	No	235 (15.2%)	110 (15.4%)	44 (18.5%)	81 (13.5%)		χ^2	V
	Febricula	365 (23.6%)	162 (22.8%)	32 (13.4%)	78 (13.0%)		<0.001	0.078 Small
	Fever	916 (59.2%)	411 (57.7%)	140 (58.8%)	365 (61.0%)		χ^2	V
	NA	125 (8.1%)	29 (4.1%)	22 (9.2%)	74 (12.4%)		0.048	0.054 Negligible
<i>Symptoms: Digestive-gastro</i>	No	1053 (68.0%)	493 (69.2%)	152 (63.9%)	408 (68.2%)		χ^2	V
	Yes	353 (22.8%)	179 (25.1%)	62 (26.1%)	112 (18.7%)		0.048	0.054 Negligible
	NA	142 (9.2%)	40 (5.6%)	24 (10.1%)	78 (13.0%)		χ^2	V
<i>Symptoms: Overall</i>	No	1 (0.1%)	0	0	1 (0.2%)		0.452	NS NS
	Yes	1547 (99.9%)	712 (100%)	238 (100%)	597 (99.8%)		K-W	η^2
	NA	0	0	0	0		<0.001	0.030 Small
<i>Symptoms: Days</i>	Median	7	7	6	6		χ^2	V
	IQR	[4, 10]	[5, 10]	[4, 9]	[4, 8]		0.001	0.100 Small
	Num. valid	1415 (91.4%)	682 (95.8%)	213 (89.5%)	520 (87.0%)		χ^2	V
<i>Emergency treatm: ACEI-AIIRB</i>	No	745 (45.1%)	426 (59.8%)	113 (47.5%)	206 (34.4%)		0.001	0.100 Small
	Yes	365 (23.6%)	167 (23.5%)	66 (27.7%)	132 (22.1%)		χ^2	V
	NA	438 (28.3%)	119 (16.7%)	59 (24.8%)	260 (43.5%)		0.002	0.086 Negligible
<i>Emergency treatm: Statin</i>	No	960 (62.0%)	496 (69.7%)	133 (55.9%)	331 (55.4%)		χ^2	V
	Yes	410 (26.5%)	172 (24.2%)	78 (32.8%)	160 (26.8%)		0.003	0.080 Negligible
	NA	178 (11.5%)	44 (6.2%)	27 (11.3%)	107 (17.9%)		χ^2	V
<i>Emergency treatm: Anticoagulant</i>	No	1406 (90.8%)	666 (93.5%)	209 (87.8%)	531 (88.8%)		0.003	0.080 Negligible
	Yes	142 (9.2%)	46 (6.5%)	29 (12.2%)	67 (11.2%)		χ^2	V
	NA	0	0	0	0		0.030	0.066 Negligible
<i>Emergency treatm: Antiplatelet</i>	No	980 (63.3%)	525 (73.7%)	162 (68.1%)	293 (49.0%)		χ^2	V
	Yes	165 (10.7%)	26 (10.3%)	73 (10.9%)	66 (11.0%)		0.030	0.066 Negligible
	NA	403 (26.0%)	114 (16.0%)	50 (21.0%)	239 (40.0%)		χ^2	V
<i>Emergency treatm: Corticosteroids</i>	No	1180 (76.2%)	567 (79.6%)	187 (78.6%)	426 (71.2%)		0.030	0.066 Negligible

Variable	Overall		Low		By severity		High		p-value	Effect size	
	n=1548		n=712 (46.0%)		Medium		n=238 (15.4%)				n=598 (38.6%)
Inhaled	145 (9.4%)		86 (12.1%)		12 (5.0%)		47 (7.9%)		0.003	0.066	Negligible
	44 (2.8%)		14 (2.0%)		18 (3.0%)		18 (3.0%)				
	179 (11.6%)		45 (6.3%)		27 (11.3%)		107 (17.9%)				
Admission status: Body temperature [°C]	37.0		37.0		36.8		37.2				
	Median		Median		Median		Median				
	IQR		IQR		IQR		IQR				
Admission status: Systolic blood pressure [mmHg]	1347 (87.0%)		667 (93.7%)		208 (87.4%)		472 (78.9%)		<0.001	0.015	Small
	127		127		133		124				
	Median		Median		Median		Median				
Admission status: Diastolic blood pressure [mmHg]	1115, 142]		[115, 139]		[117, 149]		[113, 142]		0.003	0.007	Negligible
	1339 (86.5%)		665 (93.4%)		208 (87.4%)		466 (77.9%)				
	75		77		75		74				
Admission status: Respiratory rate [min ⁻¹]	[68, 83]		[70, 85]		[66, 83]		[66, 81]		<0.001	0.019	Small
	1338 (86.4%)		665 (93.4%)		208 (87.4%)		465 (77.8%)				
	18		17		18		24				
Admission status: Heart rate [min ⁻¹]	[16, 24]		[16, 20]		[16, 20]		[18, 30]		<0.001	0.173	Large
	1021 (66.0%)		468 (65.7%)		175 (73.5%)		378 (63.2%)				
	90		92		88		90				
Admission status: SpO ₂ [%]	[80, 102]		[80, 103]		[76, 102]		[80, 102]		0.035	0.003	Negligible
	1525 (98.5%)		710 (99.7%)		237 (99.6%)		578 (96.7%)				
	95		96		95		94				
Admission status: FiO ₂ [fraction]	[93, 97]		[94, 97]		[93, 97]		[90, 96]		<0.001	0.080	Medium
	1529 (98.8%)		709 (99.6%)		236 (99.2%)		584 (97.7%)				
	0.21		0.21		0.21		0.21				
Admission status: SpO ₂ /FiO ₂ [ratio]	[0.21, 0.21]		[0.21, 0.21]		[0.21, 0.21]		[0.21, 0.21]		<0.001	0.063	Medium
	1526 (98.6%)		710 (99.7%)		236 (99.2%)		580 (97.0%)				
	452.38		457.14		452.38		438.09				
Admission status: SpO ₂ /RespRate [%/min ⁻¹]	[433.33, 461.90]		[447.62, 461.90]		[442.86, 461.90]		[390.48, 452.38]		<0.001	0.139	Medium
	1520 (98.2%)		707 (99.3%)		235 (98.7%)		578 (96.7%)				
	5.17		5.56		5.28		4.08				
Pulmonary status: Crackles	[4.00, 5.94]		[4.83, 6.06]		[4.70, 5.94]		[3.07, 5.22]		<0.001	0.198	Large
	1017 (65.7%)		468 (65.7%)		175 (73.5%)		374 (62.5%)				
	No		No		No		No				
Pulmonary status: Infiltr. X-Ray	390 (25.2%)		246 (34.6%)		45 (18.9%)		99 (16.6%)		χ ²		V
	601 (38.8%)		261 (36.7%)		70 (29.4%)		270 (45.2%)				
	NA		205 (28.8%)		123 (51.7%)		229 (38.3%)		<0.001	0.201	Small
Pulmonary status: Infiltr. type	116 (7.5%)		73 (10.3%)		22 (9.2%)		21 (3.5%)		χ ²		V
	227 (14.7%)		142 (19.9%)		36 (15.1%)		49 (8.2%)				
	65 (4.2%)		44 (6.2%)		12 (5.0%)		9 (1.5%)				
Pulmonary status: Infiltration, Num. lobes	701 (45.3%)		334 (46.9%)		109 (45.8%)		258 (43.1%)		<0.001	0.124	Small
	439 (28.4%)		119 (16.7%)		59 (24.8%)		261 (43.6%)				
	NA		74 (10.4%)		22 (9.2%)		21 (3.5%)				
Pulmonary status: Infiltration, Num. lobes	334 (21.6%)		174 (24.4%)		47 (19.7%)		113 (18.9%)		χ ²		V
	770 (49.7%)		316 (44.4%)		125 (52.5%)		329 (55.0%)				
	163 (10.5%)		102 (14.3%)		21 (8.8%)		40 (6.7%)				
Pulmonary status: Infiltration, Num. lobes	164 (10.6%)		46 (6.5%)		23 (9.7%)		95 (15.9%)		<0.001	0.127	Small
	123 (7.9%)		75 (10.5%)		22 (9.2%)		26 (4.4%)				
	253 (16.3%)		149 (20.9%)		40 (16.8%)		64 (10.7%)				
Pulmonary status: Infiltration, Num. lobes	406 (26.2%)		197 (27.7%)		68 (28.6%)		141 (23.6%)		χ ²		V
	205 (13.2%)		105 (14.7%)		35 (14.7%)		65 (10.9%)				
	188 (12.1%)		91 (12.8%)		22 (9.2%)		75 (12.5%)				
Pulmonary status: Infiltration, Num. lobes	119 (7.7%)		36 (5.1%)		17 (7.1%)		66 (11.0%)		<0.001	0.157	Small
	49 (3.2%)		12 (1.7%)		2 (0.9%)		35 (5.8%)				
	205 (13.2%)		47 (6.6%)		32 (13.4%)		126 (21.1%)				

Variable	Overall <i>n</i> =1548		Low <i>n</i> =712 (46.0%)		By severity Medium <i>n</i> =238 (15.4%)		High <i>n</i> =598 (38.6%)		<i>p</i> -value	Effect size
	Num. valid	Median IQR	Num. valid	Median IQR	Num. valid	Median IQR	Num. valid	Median IQR		
<i>Pulmonary status: Pleural effusion</i>	No Yes NA	1317 (85.1%) 37 (2.4%) 194 (12.5%)	652 (91.6%) 13 (1.8%) 47 (6.6%)	200 (84.0%) 7 (2.9%) 31 (13.0%)	465 (77.8%) 17 (2.8%) 116 (19.4%)	χ^2	<i>V</i>			
<i>Blood test: Glucose [mg/dL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	111 [99, 134] 1383 (89.3%)	107 [97, 125] 668 (93.8%)	113 [100, 143] 217 (91.2%)	117 [103, 142] 498 (83.3%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Urea [mg/dL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	34 [26, 47] 1107 (71.5%)	30 [23, 40] 592 (83.1%)	39 [30, 57] 178 (74.8%)	41 [30, 61] 337 (56.4%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Creatinine [mg/dL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	0.92 [0.75, 1.13] 1476 (95.3%)	0.85 [0.70, 1.01] 692 (97.2%)	0.97 [0.80, 1.24] 229 (96.2%)	1.00 [0.81, 1.32] 555 (92.8%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) [mg/dL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	17.0 [13.0, 23.0] 736 (47.5%)	15.0 [12.0, 20.0] 433 (60.8%)	20.3 [15.0, 27.0] 86 (36.1%)	20.0 [15.0, 28.5] 217 (36.3%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood: Sodium [mEq/L]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	138 [136, 140] 1396 (90.2%)	138 [136, 140] 673 (94.5%)	137 [136, 141] 218 (91.6%)	137 [135, 140] 505 (84.4%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) [U/L]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	27 [18, 44] 1265 (81.7%)	26 [18, 44] 639 (89.7%)	23 [15, 39] 197 (82.8%)	29 [19, 47] 429 (71.7%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) [U/L]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	301.5 [238.0, 389.8] 1162 (75.1%)	272.0 [224.5, 341.5] 555 (77.9%)	283.0 [230.0, 347.8] 186 (78.2%)	375.0 [278.0, 470.0] 421 (70.4%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: C-reactive protein (CRP) [mg/L]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	72.13 [32.30, 134.04] 1473 (95.2%)	52.06 [23.86, 102.25] 690 (96.9%)	58.46 [26.64, 119.36] 230 (96.6%)	108.30 [60.15, 186.70] 553 (92.5%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Procalcitonin (PCT) [µg/L]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	0.11 [0.06, 0.22] 1089 (70.3%)	0.08 [0.05, 0.14] 485 (68.1%)	0.09 [0.06, 0.16] 172 (72.3%)	0.17 [0.10, 0.37] 432 (72.2%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Hematocrit [%]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	41.0 [37.7, 44.1] 1371 (88.6%)	41.3 [38.6, 44.0] 663 (93.1%)	40.3 [36.8, 44.6] 215 (90.3%)	40.9 [37.1, 44.2] 493 (82.4%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Leukocytes [count/µL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	6240 [4710, 8373] 1460 (94.3%)	6100 [4705, 7900] 687 (96.5%)	6170 [4378, 8393] 226 (95.0%)	6500 [4900, 9255] 547 (91.5%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Lymphocytes [count/µL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	900 [640, 1240] 1530 (98.8%)	1000 [770, 1330] 706 (99.2%)	900 [650, 1260] 235 (98.7%)	730 [500, 1070] 589 (98.5%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Neutrophils [count/µL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	4700 [3300, 6620] 1545 (99.8%)	4345 [3200, 6040] 710 (99.7%)	4630 [3050, 6530] 238 (100%)	5100 [3570, 7600] 597 (99.8%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Monocytes [count/µL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	420 [290, 590] 1108 (71.6%)	430 [310, 580] 592 (83.1%)	480 [315, 665] 179 (75.2%)	400 [270, 560] 337 (56.4%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Basophils [count/µL]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	20 [10, 20] 684 (44.2%)	20 [10, 20] 364 (51.1%)	20 [10, 20] 127 (53.4%)	10 [10, 20] 193 (32.3%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio (NLR) [ratio]</i>	Median IQR Num. valid	4.98 [3.33, 8.61] 1529 (98.8%)	4.17 [2.92, 6.33] 705 (99.0%)	4.76 [3.43, 4.76] 235 (98.7%)	7.17 [4.19, 11.9] 589 (98.5%)	K-W	η_H^2			
<i>Blood test: Fibrinogen [mg/dL]</i>	Median	700	685	700	700	K-W	η_H^2			

Variable	Overall		Low		By severity		p-value	Effect size
	n=1548		n=712 (46.0%)		Medium	High		
Blood test: D-dimer [ng/mL]	IQR	[562, 744]	[531, 716]	[579, 702]	[650, 750]		<0.001	0.023
	Num. valid	654 (42.2%)	360 (50.6%)	107 (45.0%)	187 (31.3%)			Small
Blood test: Serum IP-10 [pg/mL]	Median	751	610	728	1000		K-W	η^2_H
	IQR	[430, 1340]	[385, 1010]	[436, 1350]	[570, 1919]		<0.001	0.059
Arterial blood gas test: SatO ₂ [%]	Num. valid	1268 (81.9%)	625 (87.8%)	195 (81.9%)	448 (74.9%)		K-W	η^2_H
	Median	93	97	89	89		<0.001	0.032
Arterial blood gas test: FiO ₂ [fraction]	IQR	[81, 100]	[85, 100]	[82, 100]	[72, 100]		K-W	η^2_H
	Num. valid	662 (42.8%)	385 (54.1%)	79 (33.2%)	198 (33.1%)		<0.001	0.093
Arterial blood gas test: SatO ₂ /FiO ₂ [ratio]	Median	95	96	95	94		K-W	η^2_H
	IQR	[93, 97]	[94, 97]	[93, 97]	[90, 96]		<0.001	0.093
COVID-19 diagn: Method	Num. valid	743 (48.0%)	386 (54.2%)	81 (34.0%)	276 (46.2%)		K-W	η^2_H
	Median	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21		<0.001	0.107
COVID-19 diagn: Days diagnosed before admission	IQR	[0.21, 0.21]	[0.21, 0.21]	[0.21, 0.21]	[0.21, 0.28]		K-W	η^2_H
	Num. valid	946 (61.1%)	439 (61.7%)	132 (55.5%)	375 (62.7%)		<0.001	0.163
COVID-19 diagn: Antigen in urine	Median	452.38	457.14	452.38	428.57		K-W	η^2_H
	IQR	[420.24, 461.90]	[447.62, 461.90]	[439.52, 461.90]	[317.59, 452.38]		<0.001	0.163
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: Chloroquine	Num. valid	730 (47.2%)	382 (53.7%)	81 (34.0%)	267 (44.6%)		χ^2	V
	Median	0	1	1	0		0.051	NS
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: Kaletra	IQR	[0, 1]	[0, 1]	[0, 1]	[0, 1]		K-W	η^2_H
	Num. valid	811 (52.4%)	444 (62.4%)	131 (55.0%)	236 (39.5%)		0.241	NS
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: Remdesivir	Yes	662 (42.8%)	319 (44.8%)	98 (41.2%)	245 (41.0%)		χ^2	V
	No	42 (2.7%)	17 (2.4%)	8 (3.4%)	17 (2.8%)		0.579	NS
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: Interferon Beta-1a	Yes	844 (54.5%)	376 (52.8%)	132 (55.5%)	336 (56.2%)		χ^2	V
	No	682 (44.1%)	301 (42.3%)	78 (32.8%)	303 (50.7%)		<0.001	0.139
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: IV corticoids	Yes	128 (18.0%)	55 (7.7%)	16 (6.7%)	18 (3.0%)		χ^2	Negligible
	No	89 (5.8%)	209 (29.4%)	99 (41.6%)	178 (29.8%)		0.019	0.062
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	Yes	486 (31.4%)	17 (2.4%)	2 (0.8%)	11 (1.8%)		χ^2	V
	No	31 (2.0%)	2 (0.3%)	6 (2.5%)	23 (3.8%)		0.001	0.085
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	Yes	485 (31.3%)	240 (33.7%)	57 (23.9%)	188 (31.4%)		χ^2	V
	No	1063 (68.7%)	472 (66.3%)	181 (76.1%)	410 (68.6%)		0.019	0.062
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	Yes	814 (52.6%)	404 (56.7%)	130 (54.6%)	280 (46.8%)		χ^2	V
	No	734 (47.4%)	308 (43.3%)	108 (45.4%)	318 (53.2%)		0.001	0.085
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	Yes	1537 (99.3%)	708 (99.4%)	235 (98.7%)	594 (99.3%)		χ^2	V
	No	11 (0.7%)	4 (0.6%)	3 (1.3%)	4 (0.7%)		0.533	NS
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	Yes	1436 (92.8%)	703 (98.7%)	229 (96.2%)	504 (84.3%)		χ^2	V
	No	112 (7.2%)	9 (1.3%)	9 (3.8%)	94 (15.7%)		<0.001	0.260
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	Yes	1162 (75.1%)	596 (83.7%)	191 (80.3%)	375 (62.7%)		χ^2	V
	Low	43 (2.8%)	24 (3.4%)	6 (2.5%)	13 (2.2%)		<0.001	0.111
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	High	105 (6.8%)	33 (4.6%)	8 (3.4%)	64 (10.7%)		χ^2	V
	No	238 (15.4%)	59 (8.3%)	33 (13.9%)	146 (24.4%)		<0.001	0.111
Emergy COVID-19 treatm: LMWH	Yes	208 (13.4%)	122 (17.1%)	24 (10.1%)	62 (10.4%)		χ^2	V
	No	208 (13.4%)	122 (17.1%)	24 (10.1%)	62 (10.4%)		<0.001	0.111

Variable	Overall		Low		By severity		p-value	Effect size
	n=1548		n=712 (46.0%)		Medium	High		
Prophylaxis Below therap. Therapeut. High risk NA	682 (44.1%)		403 (56.6%)		119 (50.0%)	160 (26.8%)		
	67 (4.3%)		16 (2.2%)		10 (4.2%)	41 (6.9%)		
	94 (6.1%)		28 (3.9%)		23 (9.7%)	43 (7.2%)		
	58 (3.7%)		24 (3.4%)		3 (1.3%)	31 (5.2%)		
	439 (28.4%)		119 (16.7%)		59 (24.8%)	261 (43.6%)		<0.001 0.191 Small
Demographics per postcode: Population density [inhab./km ²]	5950		5726		7770	7411		
	[1549, 23222]		[1282, 15903]		[2029, 23222]	[2047, 27956]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.032 Small
	1552		1617		1550	1534		
	[14.00, 18.01]		[14.25, 18.01]		[14.44, 18.01]	[13.90, 18.01]		K-W η^2
Demographics per postcode: Population under 18 years [%]	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		0.017 0.004 Negligible
	21.40		21.40		21.56	21.40		
	[18.68, 23.21]		[18.68, 23.21]		[18.68, 22.85]	[18.66, 23.21]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		0.725 NS NS
	44.40		44.40		44.40	44.40		
Demographics per postcode: Average age [years]	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		K-W η^2
	[42.81, 45.61]		[42.81, 45.95]		[42.81, 45.20]	[42.79, 45.61]		0.143 NS NS
	2.45		2.45		2.43	2.43		
	[2.34, 2.55]		[2.35, 2.54]		[2.32, 2.55]	[2.32, 2.55]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		0.139 NS NS
Demographics per postcode: Average household size [persons/house]	2754		2731		2807	2809		
	[25.56, 31.58]		[25.42, 29.82]		[25.89, 31.52]	[25.60, 33.47]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.021 Small
	13.12		13.03		12.94	13.34		
	[12.14, 15.00]		[12.14, 14.60]		[11.37, 14.98]	[12.21, 15.53]		K-W η^2
Demographics per postcode: Average personal income [k€]	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.008 Negligible
	18.43		14.99		19.22	19.40		
	[14.08, 21.34]		[13.73, 20.23]		[14.84, 21.32]	[14.99, 21.57]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.047 Small
	7.89		7.51		11.39	7.89		
Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc - PM ₁₀ [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1084 (70.0%)		579 (81.3%)		177 (74.4%)	328 (54.8%)		
	[6.89, 11.71]		[6.83, 11.54]		[7.26, 12.24]	[7.02, 11.71]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.018 Small
	52.88		53.64		55.78	51.71		
	[50.10, 56.03]		[50.43, 55.93]		[50.87, 56.19]	[50.05, 55.90]		K-W η^2
Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc - O ₃ [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.012 Small
	18.79		17.94		18.79	19.43		
	[15.77, 27.86]		[14.89, 19.43]		[16.31, 20.07]	[17.19, 31.57]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.044 Small
	5.40		5.29		5.27	5.59		
Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc - NO [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.041 Small
	[4.72, 9.08]		[4.70, 5.62]		[5.04, 6.00]	[5.23, 9.29]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.042 Small
	26.54		25.98		26.52	27.61		
	[23.44, 41.66]		[22.15, 27.61]		[23.62, 28.76]	[25.53, 45.76]		K-W η^2
Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc - SO ₂ [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.042 Small
	3.75		4.13		3.74	3.71		
	[2.36, 4.41]		[3.71, 4.54]		[3.21, 4.37]	[2.32, 4.37]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.070 Medium
	0.24		0.23		0.21	0.25		
Pollut expos: Chronic, 50 th perc - CO [mg/m^3]	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.049 Small
	[0.18, 0.30]		[0.19, 0.26]		[0.15, 0.26]	[0.21, 0.30]		K-W η^2
	1508 (97.4%)		693 (97.3%)		235 (98.7%)	580 (97.0%)		<0.001 0.049 Small
	30.93		24.10		32.91	32.41		
	[23.44, 33.77]		[22.83, 33.50]		[23.99, 34.01]	[24.10, 33.77]		K-W η^2

Variable	Overall <i>n</i> = 1548		Low <i>n</i> = 712 (46.0%)		By severity Medium <i>n</i> = 238 (15.4%)		High <i>n</i> = 598 (38.6%)		<i>p</i> -value	Effect size
	Num. valid	Median	Num. valid	Median	Num. valid	Median	Num. valid	Median		
<i>Pollut expos: Chronic, 90th perc - PM_{2.5}</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 14.85	[13.58, 21.92]	693 (97.3%) 14.76	[13.58, 21.80]	235 (98.7%) 19.79	[14.57, 22.32]	580 (97.0%) 14.85	[13.69, 21.92]	<0.001 K-W	0.031 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Chronic, 90th perc - O₃</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 70.71	[68.51, 76.26]	693 (97.3%) 70.71	[68.51, 76.05]	235 (98.7%) 72.34	[69.41, 76.29]	580 (97.0%) 70.18	[68.51, 76.26]	<0.001 K-W	0.018 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Chronic, 90th perc - NO₂</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 34.36	[28.05, 44.10]	693 (97.3%) 32.63	[26.01, 40.53]	235 (98.7%) 38.79	[29.57, 44.10]	580 (97.0%) 39.65	[30.39, 46.25]	<0.001 K-W	0.041 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Chronic, 90th perc - NO</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 15.74	[13.61, 22.93]	693 (97.3%) 15.46	[12.88, 17.62]	235 (98.7%) 17.19	[13.66, 19.76]	580 (97.0%) 17.21	[14.12, 25.25]	<0.001 K-W	0.044 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Chronic, 90th perc - NO_x</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 57.32	[46.22, 76.68]	693 (97.3%) 54.46	[43.37, 68.99]	235 (98.7%) 65.70	[47.80, 76.17]	580 (97.0%) 67.44	[50.51, 84.07]	<0.001 K-W	0.043 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Chronic, 90th perc - SO₂</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 4.76	[4.56, 6.97]	693 (97.3%) 4.66	[4.36, 6.98]	235 (98.7%) 4.69	[4.36, 6.65]	580 (97.0%) 4.72	[4.56, 6.65]	<0.001 K-W	0.045 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Chronic, 90th perc - CO</i> [mg/m^3]	1508 (97.4%) 0.32	[0.28, 0.43]	693 (97.3%) 0.32	[0.28, 0.35]	235 (98.7%) 0.31	[0.24, 0.43]	580 (97.0%) 0.35	[0.29, 0.45]	<0.001 K-W	0.044 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 50th perc - PM₁₀</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 17.31	[12.35, 20.93]	693 (97.3%) 17.49	[12.16, 21.32]	235 (98.7%) 16.11	[11.76, 20.46]	580 (97.0%) 17.27	[13.32, 20.83]	0.008 K-W	0.005 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 50th perc - PM_{2.5}</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 10.00	[12.35, 20.93]	693 (97.3%) 10.40	[11.76, 20.46]	235 (98.7%) 10.18	[11.76, 20.46]	580 (97.0%) 9.55	[13.32, 20.83]	0.001 K-W	0.011 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 50th perc - O₃</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 60.47	[54.11, 66.50]	693 (97.3%) 60.94	[54.96, 66.09]	235 (98.7%) 59.60	[55.15, 67.32]	580 (97.0%) 59.91	[52.43, 67.18]	0.703 K-W	NS η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 50th perc - NO₂</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 11.92	[8.45, 16.31]	693 (97.3%) 11.39	[8.09, 14.48]	235 (98.7%) 11.00	[7.48, 15.77]	580 (97.0%) 13.53	[10.19, 17.52]	<0.001 K-W	0.031 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 50th perc - NO</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 2.83	[2.52, 4.03]	693 (97.3%) 2.79	[2.49, 3.51]	235 (98.7%) 2.68	[2.46, 4.14]	580 (97.0%) 3.01	[2.56, 5.41]	<0.001 K-W	0.011 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 50th perc - NO_x</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 16.49	[12.12, 21.80]	693 (97.3%) 15.72	[11.89, 19.16]	235 (98.7%) 14.72	[11.15, 21.71]	580 (97.0%) 17.69	[13.81, 25.27]	<0.001 K-W	0.025 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 50th perc - SO₂</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 3.42	[2.08, 4.44]	693 (97.3%) 3.52	[3.23, 4.85]	235 (98.7%) 3.41	[2.26, 3.75]	580 (97.0%) 3.39	[1.95, 4.06]	<0.001 K-W	0.057 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 50th perc - CO</i> [mg/m^3]	1508 (97.4%) 0.22	[0.17, 0.25]	693 (97.3%) 0.22	[0.17, 0.24]	235 (98.7%) 0.21	[0.15, 0.24]	580 (97.0%) 0.23	[0.19, 0.25]	<0.001 K-W	0.020 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 90th perc - PM₁₀</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 23.03	[16.11, 25.58]	693 (97.3%) 22.84	[16.16, 25.58]	235 (98.7%) 20.27	[15.53, 24.99]	580 (97.0%) 23.69	[16.73, 25.70]	0.001 K-W	0.008 η^2_H
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 90th perc - PM_{2.5}</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	1508 (97.4%) 13.77	[11.69, 16.71]	693 (97.3%) 14.05	[12.14, 16.71]	235 (98.7%) 13.58	[11.00, 17.09]	580 (97.0%) 13.76	[11.26, 16.76]	0.750 K-W	NS η^2_H

Variable	Overall $n=1548$		Low $n=712$ (46.0%)		By severity Medium $n=238$ (15.4%)		High $n=598$ (38.6%)		p-value	Effect size
	Median IQR Num. valid									
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 90th perc - O₃</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Median IQR Num. valid	73.90 [68.34, 77.17] 1508 (97.4%)	74.46 [71.27, 77.59] 693 (97.3%)	72.11 [67.91, 77.31] 235 (98.7%)	72.84 [66.42, 76.48] 580 (97.0%)	K-W η_H^2	<0.001	0.012	Small	
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 90th perc - NO₂</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Median IQR Num. valid	17.74 [12.06, 24.98] 1508 (97.4%)	16.02 [11.88, 22.09] 693 (97.3%)	15.79 [11.03, 24.91] 235 (98.7%)	19.32 [13.35, 26.31] 580 (97.0%)	K-W η_H^2	<0.001	0.030	Small	
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 90th perc - NO</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Median IQR Num. valid	6.53 [4.06, 10.37] 1508 (97.4%)	6.04 [4.05, 8.78] 693 (97.3%)	5.03 [3.70, 10.74] 235 (98.7%)	7.43 [4.29, 11.56] 580 (97.0%)	K-W η_H^2	<0.001	0.016	Small	
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 90th perc - NOx</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Median IQR Num. valid	25.63 [18.80, 38.96] 1508 (97.4%)	24.59 [18.59, 35.19] 693 (97.3%)	23.58 [16.49, 40.35] 235 (98.7%)	28.04 [20.49, 41.62] 580 (97.0%)	K-W η_H^2	<0.001	0.024	Small	
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 90th perc - SO₂</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Median IQR Num. valid	3.63 [2.62, 5.42] 1508 (97.4%)	3.98 [3.54, 5.90] 693 (97.3%)	3.57 [2.84, 4.55] 235 (98.7%)	3.54 [2.14, 5.03] 580 (97.0%)	K-W η_H^2	<0.001	0.061	Medium	
<i>Pollut expos: Acute, 90th perc - CO</i> [mg/m^3]	Median IQR Num. valid	0.26 [0.21, 0.29] 1508 (97.4%)	0.26 [0.21, 0.29] 693 (97.3%)	0.25 [0.19, 0.28] 235 (98.7%)	0.26 [0.23, 0.30] 580 (97.0%)	K-W η_H^2	<0.001	0.012	Small	

Univariate statistical comparisons for discrete variables were performed by means of the χ^2 test, and bias-corrected Cramer's V effect size [1]. For continuous variables, univariate comparisons were made with the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test, and its corresponding η_H^2 effect size. Thresholds for interpreting effect sizes were taken from [2].

Fig 1. Cohort characteristics (1 of 7). Univariate distributions, by severity.

Fig 2. Cohort characteristics (2 of 7). Univariate distributions, by severity.

Fig 3. Cohort characteristics (3 of 7). Univariate distributions, by severity.

Fig 4. Cohort characteristics (4 of 7). Univariate distributions, by severity.

Fig 5. Cohort characteristics (5 of 7). Univariate distributions, by severity.

Fig 6. Cohort characteristics (6 of 7). Univariate distributions, by severity.

Fig 7. Cohort characteristics (7 of 7). Univariate distributions, by severity.

Fig 8. Distribution of cases. By SARS-CoV-2 pneumonia severity, and by hospital.

Fig 9. Geographical distributions for the number of cases. (a) Total, and by severity group: (b) low = green, (c) medium = orange, (d) high = red. Gray areas represent postcodes without any patient included. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 10. Socioeconomic characteristics per postcode of residence (1 of 2). Sociodemographic and economic situation (2019 census). Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 11. Socioeconomic characteristics per postcode of residence (2 of 2). Sociodemographic and economic situation (2019 census). Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 12. Chronic exposure to air pollution [throughout 2019], per postcode of residence: 50% percentile of daily values (1 of 2); (a) PM₁₀, (b) PM_{2.5}, (c) O₃, (d) NO₂. Postcodes highlighted with light-blue borders experienced levels above the annual air quality guideline levels (AQG) recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) [3]; whereas postcodes highlighted in dark-blue exceeded the daily AQG. For (c) O₃, AQG levels are respectively peak season and 8-hourly. Catalonia's air quality network did not report (b) PM_{2.5} measurements for Barcelona. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 13. Chronic exposure to air pollution [throughout 2019], per postcode of residence: 50% percentile of daily values (1 of 2); (a) NO, (b) NO_x, (c) SO₂, (d) CO. The WHO does not currently publish recommendations on neither yearly nor daily AQG levels for these pollutants. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 14. Chronic exposure to air pollution [throughout 2019], per postcode of residence: 90% percentile of daily values (1 of 2); (a) PM₁₀, (b) PM_{2.5}, (c) O₃, (d) NO₂. Postcodes highlighted with light-blue borders experienced levels above the annual air quality guideline levels (AQG) recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) [3]; whereas postcodes highlighted in dark-blue exceeded the daily AQG. For (c) O₃, AQG levels are respectively peak season and 8-hourly. Catalonia's air quality network did not report (b) PM_{2.5} measurements for Barcelona. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 15. Chronic exposure to air pollution [throughout 2019], per postcode of residence: 90% percentile of daily values (1 of 2); (a) NO, (b) NO_x, (c) SO₂, (d) CO. The WHO does not currently publish recommendations on neither yearly nor daily AQG levels for these pollutants. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 16. Acute exposure to air pollution [date range from 2020/02/15 to 2020/05/31], per postcode of residence: 50% percentile of daily values (1 of 2); (a) PM_{10} , (b) $PM_{2.5}$, (c) O_3 , (d) NO_2 . Postcodes highlighted with light-blue borders experienced levels above the annual air quality guideline levels (AQG) recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) [3]; whereas postcodes highlighted in dark-blue exceeded the daily AQG. For (c) O_3 , AQG levels are respectively peak season and 8-hourly. Catalonia's air quality network did not report (b) $PM_{2.5}$ measurements for Barcelona. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 17. Acute exposure to air pollution [date range from 2020/02/15 to 2020/05/31], per postcode of residence: 50% percentile of daily values (1 of 2); (a) NO, (b) NO_x, (c) SO₂, (d) CO. The WHO does not currently publish recommendations on neither yearly nor daily AQG levels for these pollutants. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 18. Acute exposure to air pollution [date range from 2020/02/15 to 2020/05/31], per postcode of residence: 90% percentile of daily values (1 of 2); (a) PM_{10} , (b) $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, (c) O_3 , (d) NO_2 . Postcodes highlighted with light-blue borders experienced levels above the annual air quality guideline levels (AQG) recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) [3]; whereas postcodes highlighted in dark-blue exceeded the daily AQG. For (c) O_3 , AQG levels are respectively peak season and 8-hourly. Catalonia's air quality network did not report (b) $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ measurements for Barcelona. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

Fig 19. Acute exposure to air pollution [date range from 2020/02/15 to 2020/05/31], per postcode of residence: 90% percentile of daily values (1 of 2); (a) NO, (b) NO_x, (c) SO₂, (d) CO. The WHO does not currently publish recommendations on neither yearly nor daily AQG levels for these pollutants. Zoomed-in squares focus on the urban zones serviced by the different hospitals.

References

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